

The Soil Sentinel

ISSUE 9 – MARCH 2025

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Annual Healthy Soils for a Green Recovery meeting

The third annual Healthy Soils Event was held again at The Royal Society of Edinburgh on 12th February 2025. This years event included more of a focus on engagement with 3 workshops on the topics of carbon and greenhouse gas emissions, soil contamination and adaptation. The scene for the day was to some extent set through 3 initial presentations.

Sarah Buckingham was the guest speaker this year who presented on, a soon to be completed, ClimateXchange fellowship - *Securing Scotland's soils in a changing climate*. The second presentation on the day was from Nikki Baggaley who gave an overview of soils research across the Strategic Research Programme including the development of a soil monitoring framework. The final presentation was from Kenneth Loades who showcased work on soil health indicators and soil contamination highlighting the challenges of

setting thresholds and targets. A summary of the presentations related to the Scottish Government Strategic Research programme are included in this presentation with a link provided to the slides shown.

As mentioned previously, there was also a strong workshop component to this years event. The workshops aimed to understand and prioritise stakeholder

needs in the short and longer term. At the end of the event all participants were invited to vote on which highlighted outputs from each of the workshops were a priority for information now and also those that are viewed as critical for further understanding in the future. A summary of each workshop and outputs from the voting is also included in this issue.

Soil data/indicators for decision making, thresholds and target setting

summary —Kenneth Loades, Zulin Zhang (The James Hutton Institute) and Paul Hargreaves (SRUC)

Setting targets and thresholds for specific soil health criteria is critical, both now and in the future, in understanding the status of a soil and also for the assessment of change over time. In this context, a target is defined as an indicator value desirable to reach (i.e., a known limit or achievable value), while a critical threshold is the 'minimum criteria' for that measure. Multiple approaches are available for setting these targets and thresholds (fixed, reference, distribution or relative change) with the approach taken driven by the availability of data.

Within a European context, the EU Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law) has attempted to set some thresholds and targets but questions must be asked as to how applicable these are within a Scottish context. Within the UK, the AHDB scorecard sets benchmarks for different UK soil types and climate regions in England and Wales. As part of the Healthy Soil for a Green Recovery project SRUC performed some research to understand how applicable the scorecard was within a Scottish climate in lowland grazing, north-east arable and upland catchment areas. The study

showed that all arable soils were in a moderate (54%) or poor (46%) condition with all lowland grazing samples falling within the good (49%) or moderate category (51%). Upland catchments were typically in good or moderate condition (46% in each) with 8% of soils in poor condition. Most striking from all the results was the spread of data for each area sampled, this was typically <7% in lowland grazing and arable areas, however there was a large range (>70%) in the upland, heavily peated, area.

Utilising soil health indicators for biology, chemistry and

physical soil health, The James Hutton Institute has been working with the supply chain and farmer networks to understand whether indicators can be associated with beneficial farming practices. The work is applying multiple indicators for each component of soil health across Scotland on 20 farms and 80 fields, building on previously funded Strategic Research Programme studies. The sample locations stretch from the Scottish borders in the south to north of Aberdeen, allowing spatial variability in indi-

cators to be assessed. One such indicator and proposed threshold outlined in the Soils Monitoring Law is the Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) to clay ratio, set at 1:13 (1 part carbon to 13 parts clay). Results from the study have shown that over 99% of samples were found to exceed this threshold, or target, value. However, when looking at structural stability (a measure derived from organic carbon in relation to soil silt and clay content), only 42% were found to be stable or at low risk of structural degradation.

A surprising 58% were recorded as being either degraded or at a high risk of degradation. With structure driving a number of soil functions, it provides a good example that one indicator of soil health does not provide a full picture of soil health and highlights the need for a suite of indicators to fully understand soil health and function.

One final aspect of soil health shown related to work on soil contamination and the need for ongoing monitoring. Data collected from an 8-year-old field trial highlighted that the appli-

cation of sludge and compost gradually increased polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) concentration greater than through the application of manure. It should be noted that even after 8 years of annual applications, PAH concentrations remained below the 600µg/kg threshold indicative of weakly contaminated soils within all treatments. Emerging contaminants beyond PAHs include Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) and Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs). There is a need for POP and EDC monitoring with potential impacts beyond soil due to the leaching potential when in solution and also bioaccumulation within the food web. Adverse effects of both POPs and EDCs go beyond the environment with potential risks to human health with EDCs having potential to interfere with the function of the human and animal endocrine system.

For more information please view the slides available here or contact Dr Kenneth Loades (kenneth.loades@hutton.ac.uk), Dr Zulin Zhang (zulin.zhang@hutton.ac.uk) or Dr Paul Hargreaves (paul.hargreaves@sruc.ac.uk)

Update on soils research within the Strategic Research Programme including the development of a soil monitoring framework presentation summary

— Nikki Baggaley (James Hutton Institute)

There was an overview presentation of soils work across the strategic research program.

This provided a snapshot of the work from a huge number of teams including farm staff, people with specialist expertise in soil and vegetation surveying and even the general public helping to provide data on soils on the tops of Scotland's highest mountains.

The talk covered work on how soils are changing as a result of changing management at both the Centre for Sustainable Cropping at Balruddery and experimental plots at Grievess House; Work on peatland monitoring and how data can provide information on changes in peatlands as a result of restoration and can be used to assess resilience of peatlands to a changing climate; An over-

view of studies on the investigation and mapping of transfer pathways for chemicals through riparian zones; Data collected in Scotland's alpine habitats that will provide a unique picture of change and current status from across the county; Insights into carbon cycling in forest ecosystems both from measurements of decomposition and an understanding of the fungal communities; The initial results of data from NSIS 2007-09 exploring functional relationships in soils as a way of understanding change as a result of changes in land management and climate change; Results of the statistical analysis to assess the number of points needed in a soil monitoring scheme in order to be able to detect change and how this could change based its objectives of monitoring.

Core messages from the talk were that being able to combine data from platform sites and monitoring studies across different land covers allows an assessment of soil functioning and changes that can provide evidence for policies within the context of the soil policy route map. It also highlighted how research from across

the SRP can feed into the design of a UK - four nations approach to soil monitoring.

For more information please view the slides available here or contact Dr Nikki Baggaley (nikki.baggaley@hutton.ac.uk).

Soil contamination workshop —

Chaired by Zulin Zhang and facilitated by Nikki Baggaley (The James Hutton Institute)

There was a consensus that contamination could be a real issue in Scottish soils and a lot of that concern was associated with it being an area that is developing quickly with new contaminants being identified that we don't know a lot about. Contaminants that were discussed as those of emerging concern included antimicrobial resistance, PFAS, and microplastics, but it was also suggested that there needed to be an understanding as to whether there was a "cocktail effect" caused by contaminants in combination.

There was concern that we don't have a good idea of the extent of the issue both due to a lack of data on where contaminants are and a lack of understanding about their fate and when concentrations and stocks might impact on our use of land.

As a consequence of these concerns it was agreed issues to do with how we sample and analyse our soils for a wide range of contaminants and even those yet to be identified was a priority for research. There was also a desire for communication of this research to policy makers and agency staff in the context of the need for monitoring and regulation.

Understanding and being able to remove contaminants in circular biproducts such as biochar and sewerage sludge to reduce the risks of using these products in our soils was seen as a

key priority for research. This was coupled with the need to obtain an understanding of the fate, export and transfer of contaminants both within the food-chain and to waters. Tying these aspects together was the desire for an understanding of the vulnerability of Scottish soils to accumulation and export of contaminants and how that might change with a changing climate.

For further information please contact Dr Zulin Zhang (zulin.zhang@hutton.ac.uk) or Dr Nikki Baggaley (nikki.baggaley@hutton.ac.uk)

SOIL CONTAMINATION

Top 3 priorities:

1. Optimising the removal of contaminants from circular biproducts
2. Understanding source, export, transfer and fate of contaminants (including within the food chain, waters and health)
3. Understanding the vulnerability of (Scottish) soils to contaminants

Most urgent needs:

1. Understanding the vulnerability of (Scottish) soils to contaminants
2. Standard protocols for sampling and analysis, including for unknown contaminants
3. Education for decision making and policy (e.g. sampling strategy and regulation)

Soil Carbon and Greenhouse Gases workshop —

Chaired by Kairsty Topp (SRUC) and facilitated by Eric Paterson (The James Hutton Institute)

The two round-table sessions captured contributions from Strategic Research Programme researchers, representatives from Scottish Government and wider stakeholders. There was clear, broad agreement on the importance

of soils in the context of their contribution to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and appreciation that targeted land management has potential to increase soil carbon storage and reduce GHG losses. Before getting to the con-

Climate Adaptation workshop —

Chaired by Roy Neilson and facilitated by Tracy Valentine (The James Hutton Institute)

The workshops was run twice and attended by representatives from SAC, SRUC, James Hutton Institute, Forest Research, CxC, SEPA, Natural Scotland, & Soil Association. **The current status of Scotland's soils was considered generally degraded, however compared to many parts of the world Scottish soils were considered in better condition.** The differences between the status and functional approach to soil health was discussed and emphasised that health should be maintained. There was consensus that Scottish soils should not degrade below their current level, which could happen if unambitious targets for soil health were set.

The need to consider different land use types e.g. peatland, arable, grassland, forestry and urban and the interactions between these was discussed, for example climate impacts on upland soils, having a devastating and costly downstream impact on urban areas. Such potential risks were not always considered when assessing adaptation costs. A suggested outcome was to generate potential soil risk maps by land use, i.e., develop land suitability mapping. Identified knowledge gaps included the optimal introduction of low-density trees and animals to arable systems.

Participants identified the integration of soil functions at the systems level and understanding trade-offs and synergies when aiming to improve soils for multiple functions as the highest priority and urgency such that we could predict the outcome for a specific soil and environment under specific management practices. High priority was also given to the development of cross land use, and scaled living lab(s) for Scotland,

including gradients of management intensity and climates (including erratic climates), recognising local council scale issues vs national issues and implementation plans. The first step in this would be to understand whether this was possible by building on current research sites and reserves, and networks. Research in land managers decision making, in particular, regarding novel land practices and how valuable practices can encourage decisions was also considered a priority.

For further information please contact Dr Roy Neilson (roy.neilson@hutton.ac.uk) or Dr Tracy Valentine (tracy.valentine@hutton.ac.uk)

CLIMATE ADAPTATION

Top 3 priorities:

1. Integration to system level understanding - functions. How to improve soils and measure improvement for multiple functions
2. Living lab network. Develop cross land use and scale living lab (peat, grassland, arable, forestry) including intensity gradients and climate
3. Move from 'status of soils' to 'functional projections' (will x management move the function in a positive direction?)

Most urgent needs:

1. Integration to system level understanding - functions. How to improve soils and measure improvement for multiple functions
2. Does a Living Lab already exist? Is the knowledge gap the connection between them?
3. Behaviour change, how land owners and managers make choices across systems. How to nudge/encourage changes that research suggests are beneficial.

sideration of specific issues and priorities, the groups discussed the importance of context-specificity, with different soil types and land covers having distinct controls of GHG exchanges with the atmosphere, and that a

'one-size-fits-all' approach was inappropriate. This led to consideration of the importance of understanding benefits of C-sequestration in the context of impacts on other ecosystem services, and whether it was possible to

identify priority sites for enhanced soil C-storage. While understanding how to manage peatlands for soil C-storage was considered to be well-established, it was highlighted that the evidence for other land covers was less clear. The importance of knowing where to plant trees, including for agroforestry, was considered important. In the context of agriculture, the large contribution of reactive nitrogen (from fertilisation) was highlighted as being vital to consider alongside net C storage. The discussions highlighted that there was significant scientific understanding of influences of individual agricultural managements on GHG producing processes, but that this information was seldom combined to provide whole-system understanding, limiting the capacity to support objective policy advice. From this discussion, the value of producing a synthesis 'of what we do know' as a vehicle for science-policy communication was identified.

There was discussion around the likelihood that management for soil C-storage/ reduced GHG emissions would have trade-offs with agricultural productivity, raising questions on how payments for environmental benefits, and associated land-manager behavioural change, could be implemented. It was highlighted that soils in Scotland generally have large C-stocks, and actions that con-

serve these, particularly under future climates, are of value. An issue raised was that there is increasing interest/ commercial activity in applying various (often waste) materials to soils, claiming various GHG benefits, but without any objective validation of these claims. This led to discussions on the need for standardised methods for measuring soil C-stocks, the need to utilise existing inventory data (from different sources) and relative benefits of independent, commercial and land-manager led sampling/ monitoring.

For more information contact Dr Kairsty Topp (kairsty.topp@sruc.ac.uk) or Dr Eric Patterson (eric.patterson@hutton.ac.uk)

Top 3 priorities:

1. Effective payment schemes for environmental benefit
2. Communication on current knowledge on the topic
3. Agroforestry and where to plant trees

Most urgent needs:

1. Understanding benefits and risks of carbon improvement amendments to soil
2. Standardisation for measuring carbon stocks
3. Tradeoffs between C sequestration and other ecosystem services including the association with agronomic practices.

Soil-based solutions for flood mitigation poster

David Boldrin, Maddy Giles, Mark Wilkinson (The James Hutton Institute) and Sophie E. Lundie (University of St Andrews)

Flood resilience is at the forefront of the Scottish National Adaptation Plan (2024 – 2029) to prepare Scotland for warmer, wetter winters and associated increased frequency and intensity of storms and flash floodings. Within this strategy, nature-based solutions (NBS) play a key role. Indeed, the "perfect storm" caused by the combination of climate change, loss of biodiversity, increased energy costs and competing needs for land, requires "multi-purpose solutions", that cannot be delivered by conventional technology-based solutions (e.g., grey infrastructure). The project "Achieving multi-purpose nature-based solutions", funded by Scottish Government RESAS SRP 2022-2027, aims to assess and enhance the ecosystem services provided by a selection of water-related NBS approaches. This requires a multi-scale approach spanning from fundamental mechanisms (e.g., plant-soil interactions) to

solutions aimed at implementing NBS in the wider landscape. The poster "Soil-based solutions for flood mitigation" presents research case-studies on (i) fundamental mechanisms driving hydraulic conductivity of rooted soil; (ii) hedgerow influence on soil water regulation (storage and infiltration) and (iii) soil response to the installation of 3D field margins "magic margins" to reduce runoff.

Soil sensors – Monitoring for better management poster

Paul Hargreaves (SRUC)

Funds from the South of Scotland Enterprise and Digital Dairy Chain initiatives to investigate the use of automated soil sensors in farm fields to increase the amount of data that could be collected on the soil conditions, especially, soil moisture, soil temperature and electrical conductivity. The study was to investigate the quality of the data provided, how consistent the data was and the

variation across a field to understand the number of sensors that would be needed in a field. A grid system was employed across a 5.6 ha field of winter wheat of 15 sensors at 20cm depth with an additional 5 sensors at 10cm depth. The sensors gave similar reading through time, especially for the soil temperature but varied in value most noticeably for the soil electrical conductivity. The overall data sets showed the soil

sensors gave useable data and indicated variations across the field, however, the cause of these variations would still need to be investigated.

Soil Health indicators reflecting the situation in Scotland – Are they working?

poster

Paul Hargreaves (SRUC)

Indicators for measuring the health of the soil are important both to baseline the current health of the soil and observe any future changes related to management change, as well as to benchmark soils against the health of similar soil nationally. A scorecard of indicators covering the soil chemistry, physics and biology has been suggested by AHDB for Scottish soils and work was done to investigate if these represented the current focus of soil health from those used most commonly in the research literature and if these were sufficiently robust to reflect the health of Scottish soils.

There was agreement that the AHDB indicators aligned generally with the indicators used and recommended in the research literature. The indicator for soil organic matter (SOM) was tested against various

data sets and generally there was good agreement, apart from the more upland peaty soils that had bands for good and moderate. This did not reflect well the SOM of the soils tested. Some other method could be needed for these peaty soils if it was to be included in the scorecard to reflect the large amounts of SOM in these Scottish soils.

Trophic interactions enhancing soil P— Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi have a greater role than root hairs for selecting a microbiome and enhancing rhizosphere organic P mineralization

poster

Tim George (The James Hutton Institute)

Root hairs, arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi and rhizosphere microbiome all play important roles in mycorrhizal plant phosphorus (P) absorption from soil. However, how the plant-AM fungi-rhizosphere microbiome continuum interacts to promote the use of soil P is still unclear. Here, we present results of a controlled environment experiment to reveal the effect of root hair, AM fungi and their interaction on rhizosphere microbial P cycles. Compared to root hairs, AM fungi contributed more to active microbial community assembly, functional gene recruitment and P_o mineralization. The rhizosphere microbial P_o mineralizing process contributed more than half of plant P assimilation in the P limited condition. The application of inorganic P (P_i) reduced

the effect of root hairs and AM fungi on rhizosphere microbial community assembly and P_o mineralizing ability. Our findings demonstrate the importance of AM fungi for short root hair crop species as a driving force for rhizosphere microbial recruitment and function.

Legume-based intercropping: A pathway to reduced N₂O emissions from agriculture?

poster

Luke Harrold, Kairsty Topp, Christine Watson & Robin Walker (SRUC)

Intercropping is a farming practice which involves growing two or more crops together for a period of time with the aim of reducing inputs while maintaining or improving yields. The practice could help deliver the sustainable intensification of agriculture. An intercropping experiment was conducted in Aberdeen as part of a multi-disciplinary and multi-actor meta-experiment involving 27 participants from 15 countries (three continents) aiming to exploit the benefits of intercropping to design and manage productive, diversified, resilient, profitable, environmentally friendly cropping systems.

Our focus was on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (N₂O) as well as yield performance and yield stability of intercrops vs. sole crops. A trial was set up comparing pea-only, barley-only and intercropped barley-pea with three levels of nitrogen fertilisation, zero, half and full standard rate. Preliminary results indicate that there is no significant difference between the N₂O emission from sole-barley with full rate of N-fertiliser and the intercrop with half-rate of N-fertiliser at least in the early growth stages. The results of this experiment will not only help understand the practice locally but feed into an interna-

tional project to gain a deeper understanding of the factors which influence yield outcomes.

NEW RESEARCH OUTPUT!

Front. Agr. Sci. Eng. 2025, 12(1): 47-56 <https://doi.org/10.15388/FASE-2024589>

The interplay of direct and mycorrhizal pathways for plants to efficiently acquire phosphorus from soil

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KEYWORDS
 Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, direct pathway, mycorrhizal pathway, trade-offs, organic phosphorus-mineralizing bacteria

HIGHLIGHTS

- Plants make potential trade-off between direct and mycorrhizal pathways based on C input and P gain.
- AM fungi sense soil P heterogeneity and release exudates that select for organic P-mineralizing bacteria.
- AM fungi and soil bacteria develop a C-P mutualistic exchange in organic P patches.

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ABSTRACT
 To efficiently obtain P from soil, most terrestrial plants form symbiosis with arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi and thus have two P uptake pathways, i.e., the direct pathway (DP) via roots, particularly root hairs, and the mycorrhizal pathway (MP) via AM fungal hyphae. AM fungi form an extraradical hyphal network to expand their contact area with soil and release carbon-rich compounds, which provide a high-energy habitat for soil bacteria. The bacteria affected by AM fungi support P nutrition of AM fungi by secreting extracellular phosphatases. During the P acquisition process, both DP and MP function and require C fixed by plant photosynthesis to maintain P transport. Plants make trade-offs between DP and MP based on C inputs and P benefits. This review first systematically explores the potential trade-offs between plant C inputs and P gains of DP and MP as well as the factors that influence such trade-offs. Then the response of AM fungi to soil nutrient heterogeneity and the mechanisms by which AM fungi select bacteria to mineralize organic P and

Long-term monitoring of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in soils amended with sludge, compost, and manure in a Scotland pasture poster

Zulin Zhang, Xiao Ma, Pat Cooper, Heliang Shi, Mark Osprey, David Riach (The James Hutton Institute)

Globally, there is a growing demand for the land application of nutrient-rich organic wastes (OW) as fertilizers, however, OW may also contain recalcitrant organic contaminants, such as POPs (Persistent Organic Pollutants) and emerging contaminants, particularly when applied in large quantities to land, raising concerns about the transfer of these contaminants (e.g., PAH, PFAS and microplastics etc.) and other harmful substances to the food chain. This study investigated the impact of three types of organic wastes (sludge: S, compost: C, and manure: M) on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in contaminated soil in a Scottish pasture. After eight years of this study, notable disparities in ΣPAH_{16} concentrations were observed among the different treatments, with compost-amended soil at $378 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, sludge-amended soil at $331 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, and manure-amended soil at $223 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. The concentrations of ΣPAH_{16} in soil amended with compost and sludge exhibited a linear increase with extended sampling time. According to the fitting equation for ΣPAH_{16} concentrations under organic

waste application conditions, the S-treated soil reached $1000 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (heavily contaminated soil) at the 74th year, while the C-treated soil reaches it at the 55th year. In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of considering the effects of organic waste amendments on soil PAH levels to make informed decisions in sustainable agricultural practices. It also underscores the need for ongoing research to fully understand the implications of different organic waste applications on soil health and environmental quality.

Grieve's House Tillage Trial— A tillage by rotation long-term trial poster

Tracy Valentine (The James Hutton Institute)

Policy drivers to increase soil health, reduce erosion and reduce fossil fuel inputs into arable farming are pushing farmers to reduce the level of tillage. Inversion tillage causes significant disturbance to the soil in the short term but also leads to long-term consequences such as erosion and soil degradation. Whereas non-tillage systems often suffer from the build-up of perennial weed burden. Grieve's House Tillage Trial was established in 2017 to assess soil management under transition to a non-tillage system under Scottish climatic conditions. The trial consists of 64 cropping strips, divided into four replicates, inversion vs non-inversion tillage, and two rotation systems: Spring where soil is left fallow over the winter between spring cropping, and winter where the soil is kept covered as much as possible, either by growing winter crops or by the inclusion of winter cover crops before spring crop-

ping. Each rotation is four years long. Multiple soil physical and biological indicators have been measured showing short and long-term trends in response to management. Crop yields are often reduced in the non-inversion tillage plots, but cultivar adaption to non-inversion management is possible in both main and cover crops.

NEW RESEARCH OUTPUT!

Plant Soil
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s1104-024-06987-y>

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Crop mixtures: yield responses to climate and management and impacts on seed and soil chemical composition in a Scottish-based study

R. Brooker · R. J. Pakeman · R. L. Hewison · C. Mitchell · A. C. Newton · R. Neilson · S. Raubach · P. D. Shaw · S. Verrall · A. J. Karley

Grazing of winter cereals provides valuable late winter feed while maintaining grain and straw yields poster

Luke Harrold, Niamh Barry, Kairsty Topp, Zach Reilly, David Ross, Christine Watson & Robin Walker (SRUC)

The grazing of sheep on winter cereals intended for sale used to be common practice. The rise of modern agriculture has seen the disintegration of the once integrated crop-livestock systems as well as a decrease in many soil health indicators. As pressure grows to find more sustainable alternatives to modern agricultural practices, the reintegration of livestock

and arable farming has come back into the limelight. To evaluate the feasibility of grazing sheep on winter cereals, trials were established over three years in northeast Scotland as well as at several participating farms in the region with grazed and ungrazed sites. It was hypothesised that this practice would provide adequate feed quality and

quantity to sheep while incurring no detriment to yield and potentially improving soil health. We found that even at the highest grazing intensity, where forage was grazed to bare soil, there was no significant yield penalty incurred at harvest time. We also observed reductions in severity of plant disease, increases in earthworm abundance and no im-

impact on VESS scores in grazed sites. The results show that this practice can help ease the winter feed gap while providing no detriment to yield and may help improve soil quality and potentially help reduce reliance on synthetic inputs.

Exploring the use of mineralogy as an indicator for soil functioning and health **poster**

Nia Gray-Wannell, Urmi Ghosh, Ernest Afriyie, Nikki Baggaley, Eric Paterson (The James Hutton Institute)

The objectives of this work are to explore the link between the soil mineralogy and soil health indicators, specifically epsilon (E) and the phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) profile of the soil for soil monitoring purposes. In this context E is described as a proxy for carbon decomposition and the cycling and stability of organic matter whilst PLFAs provide information on the diversity of microbial communities in soil systems. Furthermore, we aim to explore the use of Fourier transform infra-red (FTIR) as a rapid method for characterising carbon decomposition. Our initial results show clear variations with land use type, highlighting that this is a key driver for carbon decomposition and microbial community composition on the national scale. Furthermore, the work informs that soil mineralogy (as quantified by X-ray powder diffraction) affects carbon degradation rates in Scottish soils and that FTIR can be used effectively for rapid in field soil

monitoring. Quantified mineralogy from XRPD data can be used in training FTIR datasets and the integration of diverse multivariate datasets identifies emergent functional relationships.

The soil microbiome – can we use it to monitor and predict soil health and function? **poster**

Maddy Giles, Eric Paterson, U.Z. Ijaz, Cathy Hawes, Sandra Caul, Pete Hedley, Jenny Morris, Claire Cameron, Victoria Buswell (The James Hutton Institute) and Maya Subberwal (University of Glasgow)

Soils are vital to life on earth providing a wide range of ecosystem services that underpin global food production, soil carbon (C) sequestration and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Consequently, understanding and predicting soil processes is key to developing and, monitoring the efficacy of, sustainable agro-nomic systems. Understanding these relationships will be key to achieving both Scotland's Biodiversity policy and the aims of the soil health framework. Microbial communities and characterisation of the functional genes they contain has been suggested as a means of monitoring soil health and a way to manipulate soils for beneficial function. However, we still lack a fundamental understanding of these communities, how they change over space and time, what aspect of them can be predictive of function or how we need to sample them for accurate monitoring of soil health. The work presented therefore aims to

characterise long term changes in microbial communities and better understand how the functions of these communities link to soil processes. We found that microbial communities sampled at the center for sustainable cropping changed over time and that this could vary between agro-nomic amendments highlighting that microbial communities can be responsive to management, crops and climate.

Comments and upcoming issues: *The Soil Sentinel* was produced as part of the **Healthy Soils (JHI-D3-1)** project with input from **CentrePeat (JHI-D3-2)** and the **Achieving Multi-Purpose Nature Based Solutions (AiM NBS) (JHI-D2-2)** project. We acknowledge funding through the Rural & Environment Science & Analytical Services Division of the Scottish Government. This is the ninth edition of *The Soil Sentinel* with Issue 10 scheduled to be released in July 2025. If you would like to propose a contribution to the bulletin please don't hesitate to get in touch through healthysoils@sefari.scot. Also, if you would like more information on the Healthy Soils project, or have suggestions on special issues, please reach out to us!

NEW RESEARCH OUTPUTS!

DOI: 10.1111/1365-2664.14861

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Natural tree colonisation of organo-mineral soils does not provide a net carbon capture benefit at decadal timescales

Naomi C. Housego^{1,2} | Thomas C. Parker¹ | Lorna E. Street² | Elena I. Vangelova³ | Ruth J. Mitchell¹

Journal of Applied Ecology

Plant Soil (2024) 500:587–603
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s1104-024-06507-y>

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Root anatomy and biomechanical properties: improving predictions through root cortical and stele properties

G. J. Meijer | J. P. Lynch | J. G. Chimungu | K. W. Loades

Ideas and Perspectives: Potentially Large but Highly Uncertain Greenhouse Gas Emissions Resulting from Peat Erosion

Thomas C. Parker, Chris Evans, Martin G. Evans, Miriam Glendell, Richard Grayson, Joseph Holden, Changjia Li, Pengfei Li, and Rebekka R. E. Artz